

The Role of Project-Based Learning in Developing Sustainable Fashion Solutions: Insights from the Eco-Design Challenge

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Abstract

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) has gained widespread recognition as an effective approach for engaging students with real-world challenges, particularly in sustainability-related fields. By immersing students in hands-on projects, PjBL fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity, enabling learners to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations. This methodology enhances engagement while developing transferable professional skills, such as teamwork and communication, essential for career readiness. This study explores the application of PjBL within the Eco-Design Fashion Challenge (E-DFC), a project aimed at developing sustainable restaurant and bar uniforms for El Corte Inglés. Adapting the framework proposed by Krajcik and Blumenfeld (2006) and guidelines from the Buck Institute for Education (BIE), the initiative was structured into seven key elements of PjBL: "Contextualisation," which situated this challenge within its academic context; "Problematisation," introducing project regulations and the central question; "Situated Inquiry," encouraging students to explore various approaches and gain insight into El Corte Inglés' brand identity; "Design Development and Field Research," where students refined their designs, some focusing on sustainability strategies and others conducting field research on professional challenges; "Technological Tools," where students selected and applied relevant fashion design software and equipment; "Creation of Prototype," involving pattern making and sewing to produce the final uniform aligned with their inspiration, eco-design principles, and brand identity; and finally, "Results and Disclosure," which included project evaluation, the announcement of winners, prize distribution, and media dissemination. This process underscores the integration of sustainability into the design process, the use of technology to support learning, and the real-world application of fashion design principles. This exploratory case study highlights the potential of PjBL to cultivate critical thinking, creativity, and professional skills, equipping students to tackle the challenges of sustainable fashion design and contribute to a circular fashion industry.

Keywords: Fashion Design Education; Project-Based Learning; Circular Economy.

1 Introduction

Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is rooted in the educational theories of John Dewey, Jean Piaget, and Lev Vygotsky, who laid the psychological and pedagogical foundations for this approach. Dewey (1916) emphasised the importance of experiential learning and active student engagement in real-world problems. Piaget's constructivist theory (1952, 1970) reinforced the idea that knowledge is built through interaction with the environment, highlighting the role of experimentation and discovery in learning. Vygotsky (1978) introduced the concept of the zone of proximal development, underscoring the significance of social mediation and collaborative learning, both essential elements in PjBL.

These theoretical contributions shaped its core principles, including student-centred learning, knowledge construction through practice and reflection, and collaborative problem-solving. Over time, PjBL has evolved to incorporate 21st century skills such as communication, critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration – often referred to as the 4 C's (Bell, 2010; Larmer & Mergendoller, 2012). Unlike traditional teaching methods, which often prioritises content delivery, PjBL has proven to be more effective in promoting active learning, critical thinking, fostering autonomy, decision-making, and self-management (Markham et al., 2003; Bell, 2010; Gam & Banning, 2020; Lee, 2018; Lee et al., 2024).

The Buck Institute for Education (BIE) defines PjBL as a structured teaching method where students acquire knowledge and skills through extended inquiry into complex, real-world questions (Bytyqi, 2021). Instead of passively receiving information, students investigate topics, formulate the problem before developing their solution (Lima et al., 2024), and present their findings to an audience beyond the classroom, enhancing motivation and engagement (Larmer et al., 2017).

Building on these theoretical foundations, two established PjBL models were selected to structure the E-DFC: the framework proposed by Krajcik and Blumenfeld (2006), which is primarily oriented towards science education, and the guidelines developed by BIE (Larmer & Mergendoller, 2012; Larmer et al., 2015; Larmer et al., 2017), which offer a broader, interdisciplinary approach.

Krajcik and Blumenfeld (2006) define PjBL through five key elements. The first is the presence of a driving question, which defines the central problem of the project and guides the entire investigation. Secondly, students are challenged to engage in an active exploration process, where they investigate the problem within a real-world context, applying key concepts from the discipline as they progress. Collaboration is also fundamental, fostering interaction between students, teachers, and even community members, replicating the real-world challenges. Another distinguishing feature is the use of educational technology, which supports students in accomplishing tasks that might otherwise be beyond their current capabilities. Finally, PjBL culminates in the creation of tangible and shareable artefacts, allowing students to publicly showcase their learning.

With several points in common with this perspective, Larmer and Mergendoller (2012) outline eight essential components that ensure the effectiveness of PjBL: significant content, need to know, a driving question, student voice and choice, 21st-century skills, in-depth inquiry, critique and revision, and public audience. These elements structure the learning process, making it more engaging and meaningful. Teachers must design projects around key learning objectives, ensuring that students perceive the content as relevant to their academic and professional growth. Unlike traditional teaching methods that often focus on content coverage, PjBL encourages deeper understanding through active investigation and application, allowing students to internalise knowledge more effectively. A crucial factor in student engagement is the "need to know" — when students recognise the practical relevance of their learning, they become more motivated. Introducing a project with an engaging "entry event," such as a debate, a video, or a real-world scenario, helps spark curiosity and inquiry. The driving question provides a clear purpose and challenge, guiding students toward an open-ended, complex problem that requires critical thinking and exploration. Student autonomy is also a key aspect, with varying levels of freedom in choosing project themes and execution strategies. Developing 21st-century competencies is central to PjBL, ensuring that students acquire skills essential for academic and professional success. In-depth inquiry fosters problem-solving and innovation, while structured critique and revision processes help refine their work. Finally, public presentation enhances authenticity, reinforcing the importance of quality and real-world application.

Building on these perspectives, the E-DFC was structured as a collaborative initiative that reinforced the connection between education, industry, and sustainability. Organised by the University of Minho (UM) in partnership with El Corte Inglés – Grandes Armazéns, S.A., and ToBeGreen (a spin-off of the UM), the challenge took place during the 2023/2024 academic year and was designed for students in the bachelor's degree in Fashion Design and Marketing. With a strong emphasis on eco-design and circularity, participants were tasked with developing a restaurant and bar uniform for El Corte Inglés, incorporating materials sourced from a circular economy (CE), including recycled fabrics and dead stock provided by ToBeGreen. By integrating creative problem-solving with industry-driven sustainability goals, the challenge offered students a hands-on learning experience that bridged academic knowledge with professional practice, equipping them with skills to navigate

the evolving landscape of sustainable fashion. This exploratory study aims to contribute to the growing body of research on the impact of PjBL and its role in advancing sustainability in higher education, demonstrating how structured, industry-driven challenges can foster transformative learning experiences and prepare students to address real-world environmental challenges.

2 Eco-Design Fashion Challenge (E-DFC)

The E-DFC was built upon the framework developed by Krajcik and Blumenfeld (2006) and the guidelines established by the BIE (Larmer & Mergendoller, 2012; Larmer et al., 2015; Larmer et al., 2017). Both models emphasise student engagement, deep inquiry, collaboration, and real-world application. For this initiative, the structure was adapted to the specific context of the challenge and the field of fashion design, incorporating seven key elements (Figure 1) to ensure relevance and effectiveness.

Figure 1. Phases of the E-DFC, a PjBL initiative (adapted from Krajcik and Blumenfeld, 2006; Larmer & Mergendoller, 2012; Larmer et al., 2015; Larmer et al., 2017).

00 Contextualisation

Given the participants' academic background, contextualisation was essential to position the E-DFC within their studies. The sample comprised 23 third-year students from the University of Minho's Bachelor's Degree in Fashion Design and Marketing, who took part in the initiative during the 2023/2024 academic year. This undergraduate programme integrates CE principles into fashion design, preparing students to develop sustainable and innovative solutions. These concepts are progressively introduced throughout the curriculum, with a more structured focus in the discipline "Comfort and Sustainability in Fashion", where the E-DFC was implemented.

Additionally, students in this programme are already familiar with project-based work, having engaged in "Fashion Design Project", an interdisciplinary discipline spanning every semester in the first two years and extending across the entire final year. This structure fosters a holistic approach to design challenges, strengthening their ability to integrate knowledge across disciplines and reinforcing their capacity to work within a project-oriented framework.

01 Problematisation

In the first session, students were introduced to the E-DFC through a presentation of the project regulations, outlining the fundamental guidelines for developing the uniform. The session also introduced the driving question that would guide the entire creative process: "How can we, as fashion designers for El Corte Inglés, create a functional and creative restaurant and bar uniform using circular materials?" Following BIE guidelines, this question was designed to be engaging, challenging, and open-ended, sparking interest by addressing a relevant and contemporary issue. Its complexity encouraged in-depth inquiry and critical thinking, requiring students to apply the essential concepts and skills defined as learning objectives. Aligned with the Design Challenge type of question, which is answered through the creation (and often execution) of a design that effectively meets specific requirements, its formulation followed a structured approach: "How can we, as (student role), create/research/develop (task) in order to (intended goal)?" (Lee, 2018).

This session also clarified assessment criteria, available materials, and competition requirements, ensuring students fully understood the scope and constraints of the challenge. Each student had to submit a comprehensive design proposal, with outcomes classified into four product categories (Larmer et al., 2017):

- Presentation product: A mood board illustrating conceptual inspirations, colour schemes, textures, and the design's contextual background.
- Written product: A brief descriptive statement outlining the design concept and sustainability features.
- Written product: Technical sheets with front and back sketches, specifying materials, accessories, and construction details.
- Constructed product: A physical uniform prototype incorporating ToBeGreen fabrics, allowing up to 10% additional materials for aesthetic or functional enhancements.
- Media product: Visual documentation (photographs / videos) effectively presenting the prototype.

02 Situated Inquiry

In the second phase, students engaged in an exploratory tutoring session focused on situated inquiry, critically examining different approaches to addressing the challenge. This stage encouraged deeper reflection on how to structure their projects, while the tutor played a key role in identifying knowledge gaps and guiding students toward areas requiring further exploration. As the inquiry progressed, it became evident that a comprehensive understanding of El Corte Inglés' history and brand identity was crucial to ensuring the uniform design aligned with the company's visual and conceptual identity. This connection to branding, design, and visual identity principles became an integral part of the project, shaping students' design decisions. Following a project-driven learning approach, students integrated their research in different ways (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Examples of different approaches to integrating brand research into the design process, compiled from students' portfolios.

03 Design Development and Field Research

At this stage, a new tutoring session allowed students to refine their proposals, building on insights from previous phases. The focus shifted to garment design, with students exploring visual references, creating mood boards, and contextualising the concepts behind their uniforms.

Some students identified zero-waste pattern cutting as a key strategy to reinforce eco-design principles, experimenting with ways to optimise material use, minimise waste, and enhance sustainability in their designs (Figure 3). Meanwhile, others sought a deeper understanding of the practical challenges faced by restaurant and bar staff. One student even conducted surveys with industry professionals to gather insights on how workwear impacts comfort, functionality, and performance in real workplace settings (Figure 3). These field research and experimentation processes were instrumental in shaping design decisions, ensuring that final proposals balanced aesthetic appeal with practical demands.

Figure 3. Visual documentation of zero-waste pattern exploration and analysis of professional needs, including survey insights, sourced from students' portfolios.

04 Technological Tools

In line with the challenge criteria, students selected and utilised technological tools essential for the project's execution, choosing software and equipment that best supported their design and development process. Their selections reflected knowledge acquired throughout their degree, demonstrating familiarity with industry-standard tools used in fashion design. Beyond digital resources, constructing the uniform prototypes required specialised sewing equipment, including straight-stitch and overlock machines, ensuring precision in stitching, finishing, and structural integrity.

The integration of both digital and physical tools not only facilitated the realisation of creative concepts but also reinforced a structured and professional approach to the final project presentation, enhancing students' technical and practical skills in sustainable fashion design.

05 Creation of Prototype

In this phase, students applied their patternmaking and sewing skills to construct the physical prototype of the uniform (Figure 4). Throughout the process, they ensured that the final design remained faithful to the original concept, integrating eco-design principles while aligning with the brand's identity. This stage was crucial, as it materialised the project, synthesising knowledge from previous phases and transforming creative ideas into a tangible, wearable outcome.

Figure 4. Student-created uniform prototypes.

06 Results and Disclosure

The final stage of the challenge focused on the evaluation and dissemination of results, marking its conclusion and acknowledging students' efforts. The evaluation was carried out by a jury composed of representatives from the University of Minho, El Corte Inglés, and ToBeGreen, based on a structured set of criteria with specific weightings: descriptive statement (5%), mood board (5%), technical sheets with sketches (5%), physical prototype (15%), photographs and other communication materials (5%), creativity and originality of the proposal (25%), incorporation of circular design and sustainability principles (15%), and innovation and potential for real-world application (25%). Each jury member assigned a score from 0 to 10 for each parameter, and the final classification was determined by the weighted sum of all components, ensuring a comprehensive and transparent assessment process.

Following the assessment, winners and honourable mentions were announced, with the most outstanding proposals publicly presented. The results were shared during an award ceremony, featured in the YouTube programme "Já em Movimento pela Sustentabilidade," and covered in various newspapers and magazines. The first-place winner received a monetary prize, while two students were awarded paid internships at ToBeGreen. The media coverage extended across both internal and external communication channels of the organising entities (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Media coverage highlights showcasing the dissemination of the E-DFC results across various platforms.

3 Discussion

In recent years, there has been increasing emphasis on integrating CE principles into education, particularly in fashion design (Moreira, et al., 2025). Given the industry’s significant environmental impact, fashion is shifting from linear production models to sustainable and circular practices. Education is key to this transition, equipping future designers with the knowledge and skills to adopt sustainable approaches. Embedding CE principles into curricula enables educators to cultivate a new generation of designers capable of transforming the industry through innovative and responsible solutions. Research highlights the importance of developing creativity, critical thinking, and ethical responsibility to prepare designers for environmental challenges and industry transformation (Binde & Freimane, 2022; Sehnem et al., 2024; Moreira, et al., 2025; Moreira & Marques, 2025b).

PjBL has proven to be an effective method for engaging students with sustainability-related challenges. Studies show that PjBL facilitates the understanding and application of sustainability principles across different contexts (Jollands & Parthasarathy, 2013; McGibbon & Van Belle, 2015). By immersing learners in real-world scenarios, this approach fosters critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills, encouraging students to apply their knowledge to complex, practice-based challenges (Williams et al., 2017; Gam & Banning, 2020). PjBL also promotes active learning, linking theory with hands-on experience for deeper knowledge retention. In sustainability education, it has been particularly effective in teaching zero-waste design and raising awareness of resource efficiency in the design process (Gam & Banning, 2020). By addressing the multifaceted nature of sustainability, PjBL helps students connect theoretical concepts to real-world decision-making (Jollands & Parthasarathy, 2013).

The E-DFC illustrates the effectiveness of PjBL in fostering sustainability-driven design thinking among fashion students. The challenge demonstrated how structured, industry-aligned projects can bridge theoretical knowledge with practical application, reinforcing key competencies in eco-design, CE, and professional practice. One of its core strengths was its alignment with PjBL principles, particularly active learning, inquiry-based exploration, and problem-solving. The seven-phase structure allowed students to progressively refine their projects, engaging in a real-world challenge that integrated branding, functionality, and sustainability concerns. At each stage, students applied critical thinking and decision-making, whether through situated inquiry, field research, or technological exploration, ultimately producing well-informed and technically refined prototypes.

The driving question played a crucial role in shaping the learning experience, prompting students to engage deeply with sustainability challenges in fashion. By designing a uniform that aligned with El Corte Inglés’ brand

identity while incorporating circular materials, students encountered industry-relevant constraints, fostering a problem-solving mindset essential for professional practice. The design development phase revealed diverse approaches, with some students prioritising zero-waste pattern cutting, while others explored functional performance through engagement with industry professionals. This varied application of sustainability principles underscores the flexibility of PjBL, allowing students to tailor their learning pathways to personal interests and project needs.

Beyond technical skills, the E-DFC facilitated the development of soft skills essential for the 21st-century workforce, including critical thinking, creativity, autonomy, communication, and decision-making. The final stage, involving public presentations and media coverage, highlighted the importance of visibility in professional practice, enabling students to engage with a broader audience beyond academia. The internship opportunities at ToBeGreen further reinforced the challenge's industry relevance, offering students a direct entry point into the sustainable fashion sector.

Despite its strengths, some challenges emerged. The complexity of eco-design principles required intensive research and material experimentation, which was time-consuming within the constraints of the academic calendar. Additionally, while the collaborative nature of PjBL was evident, some students may have benefited from more structured guidance on integrating sustainability principles into technical decision-making. Future iterations of the E-DFC could incorporate additional workshops or mentorship with sustainability experts to further support knowledge application.

4 Conclusion

The E-DFC exemplifies how PjBL can be effectively integrated into fashion education to promote sustainable design thinking and industry preparedness. By engaging students in a structured yet flexible learning experience, the challenge bridged theoretical knowledge with hands-on application, fostering both technical and soft skills. The findings suggest that structured, industry-driven challenges play a crucial role in preparing students for the evolving demands of sustainable fashion, particularly by encouraging critical engagement with real-world constraints. Future studies could explore how PjBL initiatives in fashion education can further integrate emerging technologies and interdisciplinary collaboration, ensuring their continued relevance in an ever-changing industry.

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Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at the DataRepositóriUM:

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